

Lighthouse Farm Network Guide (MS.2)

Climate Lighthouse Farm Network Guide

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List of Abbreviations

CFD	Climate Farm Demo
NC	National Coordinator
PDF	Pilot Farm Demo
WP	Work Package
CLF	Climate Lighthouse Farm
GRLF	Global Network of Lighthouse Farms
WUR	Wageningen University and Research

Table of Contents

1. General Introduction	5
2. Defining Climate Lighthouse Farms (CLF)	5
What is a Climate Lighthouse Farm?.....	5
3. Identifying a CLF	7
Training in co-innovation and research.....	7
Tasks and Roles	8
Benefits of being CLF farmer.....	9
4. Building a resilient CLF network	9
Connection to GNLF	9
Exchange and communication.....	9
In-person exchange	9
Network of networks	10
5. Good practices for lighthouse farm network development	10

1. General Introduction

All over Europe, we find inspiring farmers, who are proving to their neighbours that the impossible, is possible. They also inspire policy makers, agri-business leaders, and other actors in the food system to think differently about how we envisage future farming systems. These are diverse farmers with commercially viable businesses, who are also engaging with research institutes and Universities to accelerate relevant knowledge and innovations, by being co-creators to the research projects they participate in. These farmers are a beacon of hope on the horizon, that guide actors in the food system towards a sustainable agriculture system that is both resilient to the changing climate and reduces the impact of the agriculture sector on our planetary boundaries. In this project, we refer to these radical farming systems as Climate Lighthouse Farms. A Climate Lighthouse Farm (CLF from now on) is a farm or community of farmers applying an innovative climate-smart farming approach and contributing to the co-creation of research agendas.

One of the European Union's key strategies to tackling climate change in the agriculture sector is through increasing participatory research in which farmers play a key role in R&I. Farmer participation is seen as key, given the massive diversity of farming systems around the EU and plurality of solutions needed. However, forward-thinking farmers are often too busy and/or do not have the right tools to advocate for themselves during the co-innovation process. The Climate Lighthouse Farm trajectory offers them guidance and advice on how to become active and well-informed participants in R&I, thus strengthening their positionality in European research infrastructure. In the Climate Farm Demo project, 1 CLF will be selected in each partner country by the end of this project based on the pool of Pilot Demo Farmers (PDF). Together, these CLFs will create a network of diverse and inspirational farming systems to show that represents how there is no silver bullet to climate smart agriculture. This project will empower these inspiring farms to be active participants in Research and Innovation (R&I), through a series of workshops, and exchange with the Global Network of Lighthouse Farms, and the development of their own network of exchange which will endure beyond the length of the Climate Farm Demo project.

In this report, we will outline a broad definition of a Climate Lighthouse Farm, provide a step-by-step guide for how National Coordinators can identify CLF in their projects, and describe how we will ensure a resilient CLF network including by building a connection with the Global Network of Lighthouse Farms.

2. Defining Climate Lighthouse Farms (CLF)

What is a Climate Lighthouse Farm?

A Lighthouse Farm is part of a network which, together, represents a mosaic of diverse solutions. Pilot Demo Farmers or Experimental Farms, which aim to inspire other farmers to implement new farming practices. Lighthouse Farms, on the other hand, aim to inspire all actors in the food system (including policy makers and agri-business leaders) to imagine new visions for the future, and learn about what changes need to be made to enable farmers to adopt new practices.

The Lighthouse Farm concept is primarily based on the Global Network of Lighthouse Farms and the definition provided by Valencia (2022) as *“successful exemplars of disruptively innovative farming*

systems (i.e. lighthouse farms) that are proving to be economically, environmentally and socially sustainable and as such already rising to the multiple challenges of a shared future that is food secure, nutritious, sustainable and resilient.” Climate Lighthouse Farm (CLF) definition has been adapted and further elaborated to support the goals and aims of the Climate Farm Demo project. For example, all CLF should contribute to climate change mitigation and/or adaptation (whereas the GNLF farms reflect a broader diversity of sustainability such as biodiversity, rural viability, and sustainable governance). Participation in R&I is also an important aspect of Lighthouse Farms. Therefore, the definition provided for Climate Farm Demo has greater emphasis on the participatory capacity of farms within R&I spaces, (e.g. Horizon Europe), as can be seen in Pillar 3 criteria below.

It is important that CLF are not considered to be “better than” other farming systems, as there are far more exceptional farms than there can be Lighthouses. Lighthouse farmers are those who want to share their knowledge and participate in research, which is not necessarily a prerequisite to be an excellent farmer. This is an important distinction to keep in mind.

A CLF must comply with all the three pillars detailed in **Table 1**. These criteria are vague by design, as they are intended to leave space for interpretation and local contextualization which is also a key aspect of Lighthouse Farms. CLF should be identified by local (national or regional) actors who can verify the local relevance of the farms. Commercially viable refers to a farming system that is able to sustain itself from farming-related activities, represents a viable business model, and is not an experimental research station.

Pillar 1 Climate Smart Farming System	Pillar 2 Demonstration and Communication	Pillar 3 Co-innovation and research
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Front-runner in climate-smart farming systems • Can be a single farm, or group of farmers in an area which are all applying similar climate-smart farming approaches • The farming system must be commercially viable, and therefore able to sustain itself from farming-related activities. • The farmer(s) have experience, knowledge, and a willingness to learn • The European network must be diverse, so WP1 will ensure that each candidate farm will contribute a unique approach which ideally reflects relevant solutions for a given region (diversity in gender and age must also be accounted for). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Has been an active and reliable participant as a PDF. • Willing and interested to share narrative stories, photos, and videos about their farming system to all types of actors across the food system, such as policy makers, consumer, and farmers. • Interested in providing tours for day visitors, including groups. • Able to ensure that visiting researchers can find adequate accommodation for medium and long-term (multiple months) stays. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publish anonymised data whether it is positive, negative, or neutral. • Able to be part of a research consortium/project with academic institutions, in which long term research and co-innovation can be developed. • Capacity and knowledge to support MSc/PhD studies on-farm. • Basic knowledge on research co-development

Table 1. Defining a Climate Lighthouse Farm in 3 Pillars

3. Identifying a CLF

National Coordinators will be tasked with identifying 2-3 candidate CLFs by the end of Year 4. Before arriving at that stage, they can follow the flowchart below to help guide how to identify a CLF. Importantly: all CLF should first participate as PDF. This is an easy way to build rapport and evaluate the farm's interest in engaging with R&I projects, such as the Climate Farm Demo project.

Figure 1. Flowchart process to identify a Climate Lighthouse Farm

Training in co-innovation and research

For those CLFs which do not yet comply with Pillar 3 criteria, they will be invited to participate in two workshops, organized by WUR. These workshops will provide training and introduction on what being an active participant in R&I infrastructure in Europe, and will allow them an opportunity to exchange with the Global Network of Lighthouse Farms.

R&I Workshop 1: Introduction to relevant European research networks and infrastructure (e.g. TP Organics, Horizon Europe, etc.)

R&I Workshop 2: Exchange and learning with the Global Network of Lighthouse Farms

- Lessons learned from participating in R&I infrastructure as a farm; working with Research institutes and Universities; supervising and hosting MSc and PhD students.

Timeline for National Coordinators

YEAR	WHEN	ACTIVITY	LEAD
2023	Oct.	NC receive CLF Network Guide document	WP1
2024	March	CLF info session for NC	WUR
2025	2- weeks before Annual Meeting	NC submit 2-6 candidate CLF from PDF pool	NC
	Oct? Annual Meeting	CLF network workshop for NC to ensure diversity of farms in network	WUR
2026	Jan. – Oct.	R&I Workshop 1 for candidate CLF R&I Workshop 2 for candidate CLF	WUR
	Oct? Annual Meeting	NC submit 1-2 CLF	NC
2027	Jan. – April.	CLF announced – Social Media campaigns	
	Jan. – Dec.	Virtual facilitation of Network (e.g. WhatsApp group)	
2028	Oct? Annual Meeting	CLF invited to final AM	NC?

Tasks and Roles

National Coordinators, along with local partners, will be tasked with identifying potential Climate Lighthouse Farmers, and sharing with them the opportunity to be part of a network of diverse farming systems around Europe, which each contribute a unique approach to tackling climate change, either through adaptation or mitigation techniques. It is important to note that National Coordinators will be in charge of submitting 2-3 potential CLFs to WP1. (To manage expectations, it's not necessary for the farms to know that they are a potential CLF, it is possible that they will only be informed of their candidacy once they are selected and requested to join). WP1 will ensure there is a diversity of e.g. climate-smart practices, farm sizes, and gender and provide a recommendation to National Coordinators for which candidate farm would best contribute to that 'mosaic of solutions.' There will be a workshop for National Coordinators in the 3rd Annual Meeting of Climate Farm Demo.

WUR, Ensure diversity of climate lighthouse farms are selected by evaluating in year 5 all the candidates. Organise workshops to train candidate lighthouse farms on how to be active participants in

co-innovation and research (Pillar 3), and facilitate network of exchange between selected Lighthouse Farms and Global Network of Lighthouse Farms. Develop guidelines on how the Climate Farm Demo project will support in the communication and share the stories of the selected Climate Lighthouse Farms.

Benefits of being CLF farmer

When approaching potential CLF, they should be informed of the benefits of being a CLF. This information below can and should be shared with them by National Coordinators!

Recognition and Media Coverage: Farmers are working extremely hard day in and day out! We intend to help celebrate their work through a profile on the Climate Farm Demo website and a video celebrating their hard work.

Training to participate in R&I: Farmers currently participate in many research projects without any compensation, Climate Farm Demo included. This training can empower them to be active participants in the R&I landscape, by learning from those who have already been partners in research projects, and thereby helped define the research and the resources they need for participation. This is an investment that can help in future project proposals.

Network development: Farmers love to learn from each other and exchange knowledge. This is an opportunity for farmers to be part of a network of international, yet like-minded individuals who are pushing the boundaries and discovering new ways of identifying future-proof climate-smart solutions. This network of CLF will provide them the platform to exchange and meet ideally one time in person (to be determined).

4. Building a resilient CLF network

Connection to GNLF

The candidate CLFs will participate in an in-person workshop (to be confirmed) with the Global Network of Lighthouse Farmers (GNLF) to facilitate knowledge exchange, particularly around participation in R&I. The GNLF have many years of experience to share, and provide inspiration on how to be active participants in R&I infrastructure. Additionally, the Climate Demo Farm page will be connected to the GNLF website, to increase global visibility for the CLF.

Exchange and communication

Based on the CLF selected, we will create a platform for the farmers to share their stories with each other. For the final year of the project, after an in-person meeting, a Whatsapp group, or other format will be created for those who wish to stay connected.

In-person exchange

An initial, in person moment of meeting will be critical to ensuring long-term longevity of the CLF network. For the farmers to meet in person, visit a farm, and share their stories is vital for creating trust and building this mutual interest in each other's developments. CLF will be invited to the final Annual Meeting.

Network of networks

Each Climate Lighthouse Farm will be best placed to succeed if they have a partner to „champion“ their work, and support them. Normally, this is a local NGO, research institute, governmental body, or University that has a history of working with the farm. (It may be the National Coordinators, if relevant). Their participation in the network as a support to the farm is critical to helping the farmer be a confident and active participant in an international network. We will encourage this collaboration, especially in the cases where the farmer does not speak English.

5. Good practices for lighthouse farm network development

Lighthouse Farms are meant to be inspirations, not models to be copy and pasted across Europe. They teach us lessons about what is possible, and help visualize alternative futures. Farmers should therefore not be told that they must follow a pre-destined trajectory to become any particular type of farm. A lighthouse farm is not a destination for the future, but a tool for learning about the future.

Having said that, Lighthouse farms themselves are not static, frozen in time. They are vulnerable to changes like any type of farming business and could also close down. That is why Lighthouse networks must be dynamic and facilitated, with influx and outflux of farms as a natural and expected process.

One of the final deliverables of this project will be a guide on good practices for establishing a Lighthouse Farm Network, and will build on the experiences of the the National Coordinators in identifying and engaging with Lighthouse Farms, as well as the of the Lighthouse Farmers themselves. Surveys will be sent out to all National Coordinators and Lighthouse Farms to report on their experiences.

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